
***Isocrania* (Jaekel 1902) from the Late Maastrichtian
'Tuffeau jaunâtre à Thecidea papillata'-bed (Jauche Member)**

Nick VAN LIEFFERINGE

TAXONOMY

Kingdom: Animalia

Phylum: Brachiopoda

Class: Craniata

Order: Craniida

Family: Craniidae

Genus: *Isocrania* (Jaekel 1902)

Species: *Isocrania* sp.

Author Citation: Jaekel 1902

GEOLOGICAL TIME SCALE

Eon: Phanerozoic

Era: Mesozoic

Period: Cretaceous

Sub Period: None

Epoch: Late

International Age: Maastrichtian

STRATIGRAPHY

The fossil is associated with a coarse-grained biocalcarenite ("Tuffeau jaunâtre à Thecidea papillata"-bed), part of the (Late Maastrichtian) Jauche Member (**Bless et al.** 1990).

PROVENANCE

Collector: Nick Van Liefferinge (NVL)

Date Collected: 02/15/2025

Acquired by: Field collection

LOCATION

Jauche-la-Marne
Orp-Jauche
Walloon Brabant
Belgium

MORE INFO

"Craniid brachiopods have often been considered problematic fossils, which explains why they have been the subject of numerous taxonomic debates" (**Simon** 2007).

REFERENCES

Bless M.J.M., Felder P.J. & Jagt J.W.M. 1990: Repeated Tethyan influences in the Early Campanian to Middle Late Maastrichtian successions of Folx-les-Caves and Orp-le-Petit (Eastern Brabant Massif, Belgium), *Annales de la Société Géologique de Belgique*, T. 113 (fascicule 2), pp. 179-197.

Simon E. 2007: A new Late Maastrichtian species of *Isocrania* (Brachiopoda, Craniidae) from The Netherlands and Belgium, *Bulletin van het Koninklijk Belgisch Instituut voor Natuurwetenschappen* 77, pp. 141-157.

Fig. 1